

Anthracene-based new dinucleating ligand supported assembly of bridged dicopper(II) and dizinc(II) centers for the exploration of sugar-metal ion interactions[†]

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Abstract : Two new, a dinuclear copper(II) and a dinuclear zinc(II) complexes of an anthracene-based new dinucleating ligand, *N,N'*-bis[anthracene-2-ylmethyl]-*N,N'*-bis[2-hydroxyethyl]-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol (H_3L) have been synthesized and characterized. In methanol, the reaction of stoichiometric amounts of $Cu(OAc)_2 \cdot H_2O$ and the ligand H_3L in the presence of NaOH at ambient temperature afforded a new dinuclear copper(II) complex, $[Cu_2L(\mu-OAc)(H_2O)_2]$ (1). Similarly, in methanol, the reaction of stoichiometric amounts of $ZnCl_2$ and the ligand H_3L in the presence of NaOH yielded a new dinuclear zinc(II) complex, $[Zn_2L(\mu-Cl)(H_2O)_2]$ (2). The complexes 1 and 2 are fully characterized by different analytical techniques. Both the two complexes have been evaluated for their binding interactions with biologically important monosaccharides, such as, D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose in alkaline dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) solution by a combined approach of UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopic techniques. All the monosaccharides bind to the metal complexes in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The binding constants of the sugar-bound dinuclear copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes have been determined from both UV-Vis and fluorescence titration experiments.

Keywords : Dinucleating ligand, copper(II) complex, zinc(II) complex, sugar binding, UV-Vis spectra, fluorescence spectra.

Introduction

The interaction between carbohydrates and metal ions is of increasing interest as it occurs during many important biological processes involving structural support in membrane systems, cell-cell adhesion, transmission of nerve impulses and the regulation of sugar metabolizing metalloenzymes¹⁻⁵. There are many sugar metabolizing enzymes that have been shown to function with metal ions such as Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in the active sites⁶⁻¹⁰. Metal-carbohydrate interactions have also been exploited in metal-catalyzed enantioselective synthesis. Metal-carbohydrate complexes are also used as potential radiopharmaceutical and imaging reagents, and catalysts for the production of hydrogen from sugars¹¹⁻¹⁶. Wong and Sharon has shown the carbohydrate recognition using synthetic receptors in relation to the important role of sugars in many biological processes^{17,18}. Furthermore, the carbohydrates are also considered as the potential ligands not only due to their extensive presence in the biological systems, but also due to the presence of multi-hydroxy functionality and well-defined stereochemistry

suitable for metal coordination. Although metal-carbohydrate coordination chemistry is of fundamental importance to these processes, investigation on the structures and characteristics of carbohydrate coordination compounds is often limited compared to the complexes derived from sugars with strong coordinating amino groups^{19,20}.

In general, saccharides are very versatile, "chameleon"-like ligands due to their large number of nearly equivalent donor sites and also due to equilibria between several isomers. In the past several years, Rao and co-workers have contributed immensely to the growth of the subject of transition metal-carbohydrate chemistry and biology²¹. They have developed the simple synthetic strategies in the case of VO^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and MoO_4^{2-} ions. In contrast, carbohydrate-metal assemblies based on carbohydrate-containing ligands with weak coordinating alcoholic, aldehyde, or ketone oxygen donor atoms remain poorly understood²². Due to the low stability of the complexes in neutral or acidic aqueous solution, the characterization of the equilibria occurring during the interaction is very difficult and

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

often reaches experimental limitations²³. Recently, we have reported the dinuclear manganese(II), cobalt(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of carboxylate-rich dinucleating ligands which have shown the excellent binding interactions towards the biologically important monosaccharides in aqueous-alkaline solution^{24–26}. The introduction of polycyclic aromatics, such as anthracene skeleton within these type of dinucleating ligand systems definitely helps to assess the binding interactions by spectrofluorimetric technique. In this paper, we report the synthesis, characterization and sugar binding affinity of two new dinuclear copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of an anthracene-based dinucleating ligand.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and general characterization :

The symmetrical dinucleating ligand, H₃L (Fig. 1) with central pendant alcoholic arm has been prepared following three steps reactions. The preparation of the precursor reduced Schiff base ligand, 1,3-bis[(anthracene-2-ylmethyl)-amino]-propan-2-ol, has been achieved by the condensation of stoichiometric amounts of 9-anthracene-carboxaldehyde and 1,3-diamino-propan-2-ol in methanol under stirring conditions at ambient temperature, followed by the reduction using NaBH₄ in methanol-*N,N*-dimethylformamide (9 : 1; v/v) solution. Alkylation of the secondary amines of 1,3-bis[(anthracene-2-ylmethyl)-amino]-propan-2-ol with stoichiometric amounts of iodoethanol yielded the final ligand, H₃L. The ligand H₃L is characterized by elemental analysis, FTIR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic analyses.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the ligand H₃L.

The reaction of Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O with the ligand H₃L in 2 : 1 molar ratio in the presence of a strong base, NaOH at pH ~9 in methanol produced a green dinuclear complex, [Cu₂L(μ-OAc)(H₂O)₂] (1). However, the reaction of ZnCl₂ with H₃L in 2 : 1 molar ratio in the presence of

NaOH at pH ~9 in methanol formed a light yellow dinuclear complex, [Zn₂L(μ-Cl)(H₂O)₂] (2). The complexes 1 and 2 (Fig. 2) are fully characterized using the analytical techniques such as elemental analysis, solution electrical conductivity, FTIR, UV-Vis, ¹H, and ¹³C NMR spectral analyses. The molar conductivity values of complexes 1 and 2 in DMF are 17 and 24 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ respectively, at room temperature, indicating the nonelectrolytic formulations of the complexes.

M₁ = M₂ = Cu(II); X = CH₃CO₂⁻, Complex 1
M₁ = M₂ = Zn(II), X = Cl⁻, Complex 2

Fig. 2. Chemical structure of dinuclear copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes.

UV-Vis spectroscopy and sugar binding :

The strength of binding interactions of the metal complexes isolated from sugars or sugar-type ligands containing hydroxyl or carbonyl oxygen donor atoms only, is very weak in neutral or acidic solutions^{4,27}. Therefore, the binding events of the dinuclear complexes 1 and 2 with D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose have been examined by UV-Vis spectroscopy in DMSO solution at highly alkaline pH. The binding with sugar substrates leads to a gradual increase in the absorption intensities accompanied by a red shift in the UV-Vis spectra of this type of complexes, as the complex/sugar assembly via coordination is expected to perturb the ligand based electronic transitions of the complexes. The dinuclear copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes interact with sugar substrates at pH ~ 12.5 to yield 1 : 1 complex/sugar bound assemblies, resulting in the formation of two-state systems which is consistent with some previously studied mononuclear and dinuclear manganese(II), cobalt(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes^{24–26,28}. The representative UV-Vis spectra obtained during the titration of complex 1 with D-glucose and D-xylose are given in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. The UV-Vis spectra clearly demonstrate significant

Fig. 3. UV-Vis spectra obtained during the titration of dinuclear copper(II) complex (**1**) ($1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$) with D-glucose at room temperature in unbuffered, alkaline DMSO solution (pH ~ 12.5); the concentration of D-glucose were varied from $0-1.7 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectra obtained during the titration of dinuclear copper(II) complex (**1**) ($1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$) with D-xylose at room temperature in unbuffered, alkaline DMSO solution (pH ~ 12.5); the concentration of D-xylose were varied from $0-1.7 \times 10^{-3} M$.

hyperchromism in the charge transfer regions with a red shift of 2–3 nm of the absorption maxima of complex **1** ($\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{1}) = 336 \text{ nm}, 353 \text{ nm}, 370 \text{ nm}, 390 \text{ nm}$) upon D-glucose binding ($\lambda_{\max} = 339 \text{ nm}, 355 \text{ nm}, 372 \text{ nm}, 392 \text{ nm}$; Fig. 3), a red-shift of 2–3 nm upon D-xylose binding ($\lambda_{\max} = 338 \text{ nm}, 356 \text{ nm}, 373 \text{ nm}, 392 \text{ nm}$; Fig. 4) and a red-shift of 2–3 nm upon D-mannose binding ($\lambda_{\max} = 338 \text{ nm}, 356 \text{ nm}, 373 \text{ nm}, 393 \text{ nm}$).

Similarly, the UV-Vis spectra indicate a red-shift of 2–3 nm of the absorption maxima of complex **2** ($\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{2}) = 335 \text{ nm}, 351 \text{ nm}, 370 \text{ nm}, 389 \text{ nm}$) during D-glucose binding ($\lambda_{\max} = 337 \text{ nm}, 353 \text{ nm}, 373 \text{ nm}, 391 \text{ nm}$), a red-shift of 2–3 nm during D-xylose binding ($\lambda_{\max} = 337 \text{ nm}, 353 \text{ nm}, 373 \text{ nm}, 392 \text{ nm}$) and a red-shift of 2–5 nm during D-mannose binding ($\lambda_{\max} = 338 \text{ nm}, 354 \text{ nm}, 375 \text{ nm}, 393 \text{ nm}$; Fig. 5). The hyperchromism along with substantial red-shift for complexes **1** and **2** revealed the active participation of sugar substrates in the binding events.

Fig. 5. UV-Vis spectra obtained during the titration of dinuclear zinc(II) complex (**2**) ($1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$) with D-mannose at room temperature in unbuffered, alkaline DMSO solution (pH ~ 12.5); the concentration of D-mannose were varied from $0-1.7 \times 10^{-3} M$.

The stoichiometry²⁹ of sugar bound complex formed from the complex and sugar is 1 : 1 confirmed by the linear fit of data as given in the representative Figs. 6 and Fig. 7. If the system contains only one light absorbing species (i.e. metal complex), no complex/sugar bound product formation takes place and the slopes of the linearly fitted data for corresponding wavelength pairs in systems containing complex or complex and sugar would be alike. This is not observed here; therefore, the binding between complex and sugar takes place and the sugar-bound copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes are produced (Fig. 6 and Fig. 7).

A representative binding isotherm plot of complex **1** upon binding of D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose is shown in Fig. 8. The binding constants of the sugar-bound copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes are calculated from the

Fig. 6. Plot of differences in selected absorbances $\Delta A_n = (A_{n,j} - A_{n,k})$ over $\Delta A_{370\text{nm}} = (A_{370\text{nm},j} - A_{370\text{nm},k})$ from titration of dinuclear copper(II) complex (1) with D-glucose at $n = 354 \text{ nm}$ (■) and 391 nm (●) for solution j containing complex 1 and D-glucose and solution k containing complex 1 at $V_t = 3 \text{ ml}$, $[\text{complex 1}]_t = 1.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $t = \text{total}$, $A_{370\text{nm}, \text{complex 1}} = 1.854$, $A_{354\text{nm}, \text{complex 1}} = 1.344$, $A_{391\text{nm}, \text{complex 1}} = 1.679$, $\text{pH} \sim 12.5$, room temperature.

Fig. 7. Plot of differences in selected absorbances $\Delta A_n = (A_{n,j} - A_{n,k})$ over $\Delta A_{370\text{nm}} = (A_{370\text{nm},j} - A_{370\text{nm},k})$ from titration of dinuclear zinc(II) complex (2) with D-mannose at $n = 354 \text{ nm}$ (●) and 391 nm (■) for solution j containing complex 2 and D-mannose and solution k containing complex 2 at $V_t = 3 \text{ ml}$, $[\text{complex 2}]_t = 1.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $t = \text{total}$, $A_{370\text{nm}, \text{complex 2}} = 1.801$, $A_{354\text{nm}, \text{complex 2}} = 1.171$, $A_{391\text{nm}, \text{complex 2}} = 1.714$, $\text{pH} \sim 12.5$, room temperature.

UV-Vis titration experiments by the method of Rose and Drago³⁰ and the values are observed to be $1.261 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $1.600 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $2.452 \times 10^2 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $1.323 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $1.124 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $2.820 \times 10^2 \text{ M}^{-1}$, corresponding to complex 1/D-glucose, complex 1/D-xylose, complex 1/D-mannose, complex 2/D-glucose, complex 2/

D-xylose and complex 2/D-mannose products, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1. Binding constant (K_b) values of copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes with sugar substrates in alkaline DMSO solution

Complex	Sugar	UV-Vis	Fluorescence
		$K_b \text{ (M}^{-1}\text{)}$	$K_b \text{ (M}^{-1}\text{)}$
1	D-Glucose	1.261×10^3	1.128×10^3
	D-Xylose	1.600×10^3	1.549×10^3
	D-Mannose	2.452×10^2	2.011×10^2
2	D-Glucose	1.323×10^3	8.389×10^2
	D-Xylose	1.124×10^3	1.035×10^3
	D-Mannose	2.820×10^2	1.227×10^2

Fig. 8. Binding isotherm plot obtained during the titration of dinuclear copper(II) complex (1) ($1.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) with D-glucose (■), D-xylose (▲) and D-mannose (●) with each $0-1.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

Fluorescence spectroscopy and sugar binding :

In order to further investigate the binding interaction of complexes 1 and 2 with sugar substrates, fluorescence titration experiments have been carried out in alkaline DMSO solution. Complexes 1 and 2 are luminescent in DMSO at $\text{pH} \sim 12.5$ at room temperature, when excited at 370 nm . The concentration dependence of the change in the fluorescence intensity of complex 1 upon addition of sugar substrates is shown in the representative Fig. 9.

From the Fig. 9, it is clearly evident that upon increasing the concentration of D-glucose a gradual decrease in the fluorescence intensity accompanied by a significant red shift has been observed. Similarly, upon increasing the concentration of D-xylose and D-mannose a gradual decrease in the fluorescence intensity accompanied by a

Fig. 9. Emission spectra of complex **1** in alkaline DMSO solution ($6.25 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\lambda_{\text{exi}} = 370 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{emi}} = 416 \text{ nm}$) as a function of concentration of the D-glucose ($0-1.3 \times 10^{-3} M$). Arrow indicates the change in emission intensity with respect to various concentrations of D-glucose.

Fig. 10. Emission spectra of complex **2** in alkaline DMSO solution ($6.25 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\lambda_{\text{exi}} = 370 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{emi}} = 417 \text{ nm}$) as a function of concentration of the D-mannose ($0-1.3 \times 10^{-3} M$). Arrow indicates the change in emission intensity with respect to various concentrations of D-mannose.

substantial red shift has been observed. Following the same procedure, the fluorescence titration experiments of complex **2** with sugar substrates have been executed. The fluorescence spectra show that there is a gradual decrease in the fluorescence intensity along with a red shift in the presence of increasing concentration of D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose. A representative fluorescence spectra obtained during the titration of complex **2** with D-mannose is shown in Fig. 10. The quenching effect with observed red shift signifies the interaction of complexes **1** and **2** with the sugar substrates. The observed change in fluorescence intensity is most likely due to the perturbation of the ligand field transitions of the metal complexes upon coordination-cum-binding of the sugar substrates.

The D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose binding constant values of complexes **1** and **2** evaluated from $I_0/\Delta I$ versus $1/[\text{sugar}]$ plots are found to be $1.128 \times 10^3 M^{-1}$, $1.549 \times 10^3 M^{-1}$, $2.011 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$, $8.389 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$, $1.035 \times 10^3 M^{-1}$ and $1.227 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$ (Table 1), corresponding to complex **1**/D-glucose, complex **1**/D-xylose, complex **1**/D-mannose, complex **2**/D-glucose, complex **2**/D-xylose and complex **2**/D-mannose products, respectively. The binding constant values obtained from UV-Vis and fluorescence titration experiments suggest that both the complexes **1** and **2** interact with D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose comparably under strongly binding condition,

i.e. at highly alkaline solution. Both the complexes **1** and **2** show quite more preferences during binding towards D-glucose and D-xylose over D-mannose which differ in the configuration of the hydroxyl group at C-2 only. The calculated binding constant values of sugar-bound copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes are comparable to the reported mononuclear and dinuclear copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes^{25,31-33}. Comparing these binding constant values with the literature data, it can also be suggested that the sugar-bound dinuclear copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes are practically stable in solution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the synthesis and characterization of a dinuclear copper(II) complex and a dinuclear zinc(II) complex of an anthracene-based new symmetrical dinucleating ligand have been reported. These two complexes have been evaluated for their binding interactions with biologically important monosaccharides (D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose) in alkaline solution. Both the complexes **1** and **2** show excellent chelating-cum-binding ability towards D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose. The binding events have been studied by a combined approach of UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopic techniques. The examples described in this paper give a representative sampling of some of the recent progress in the field of carbohydrate mimetic design. A number of carbohydrates has success-

fully been mimicked with simpler, more synthetically accessible, and more stable coordination compounds. The results reported here will positively offer the important structural and functional information with relevance to the various important sugar-metabolizing metalloenzymes.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

9-Anthracenecarboxaldehyde, 1,3-diamino-2-propanol, iodoethanol, D-glucose, D-xylose and D-mannose were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH, Germany. Copper acetate monohydrate, zinc chloride, sodium hydroxide, potassium carbonate and sodium borohydride were purchased from Merck, India. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade materials and used as received from commercial sources without further purification. Microanalyses (C, H, N) were carried out using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O Series II elemental analyzer. FTIR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer L120-000A spectrometer (200–4000 cm^{-1}). ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker AC 400 NMR spectrometer. UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV 1800 (190–1100 nm) (1 cm quartz cell) spectrophotometer. The solution electrical conductivity was obtained with a METTLER TOLEDO Five EASYTM Plus FEP 30 digital conductivity meter with a solute concentration of about 10^{-3} M.

Synthesis of *N,N'*-bis[anthracene-2-ylmethyl]-*N,N'*-bis[2-hydroxyethyl]-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol (H_3L) :

A solution of 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde (2.000 g, 9.69 mmol) in 50 ml methanol was added to a solution of 1,3-diamino-propan-2-ol (0.436 g, 4.85 mmol) in 10 ml methanol. The solution was stirred for ~ 1 h and a yellow solid product was precipitated. The product was collected by filtration, washed with methanol and dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} . Yield : 1.80 g (80%). The product was characterized as 1,3-bis[(anthracene-2-ylmethylene)-amino]-propan-2-ol. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}$: C, 84.95; H, 5.62; N, 6.00. Found : C, 84.87; H, 5.72; N, 6.09%; FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu = 3378(\text{b}), 3048(\text{b}), 2922(\text{s}), 1641(\text{s}), 1442(\text{s}), 1382(\text{s}), 1159(\text{s}), 1097(\text{s}), 1023(\text{s}), 883(\text{s}), 785(\text{s}), 729(\text{s})$; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , room temperature, δ) : 9.54 (2H, s), 8.56 (4H, d), 8.51 (2H, s), 8.03 (4H, d), 7.36–7.54 (8H, m), 4.63–4.67 (1H, m), 4.29–4.33 (2H, m), 4.14–4.19 (2H, m).

To a solution of 1,3-bis[(anthracene-2-ylmethylene)-amino]-propan-2-ol (0.940 g, 2.00 mmol) in methanol-*N,N*-dimethylformamide (9 : 1; v/v), excess NaBH_4 (0.230 g, 6.00 mmol) was added in portions while stirring. The yellow color was slightly discharged. Then the solution was refluxed for another 2 h. The solution was filtered to discard any insoluble precipitate. The clear filtrate was kept overnight at 0 °C resulting in the precipitation of a light yellow crystalline product. The product was collected by filtration, washed with methanol and water, and dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} . Yield : 0.76 g (81%). The product was characterized as 1,3-bis[(anthracene-2-ylmethyl)-amino]-propan-2-ol. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}$: C, 84.22; H, 6.43; N, 5.95. Found : C, 84.32; H, 6.31; N, 6.02%; FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu = 3292(\text{s}), 3052(\text{s}), 2899(\text{s}), 1662(\text{s}), 1623(\text{s}), 1445(\text{s}), 1331(\text{s}), 1157(\text{s}), 1117(\text{s}), 1032(\text{s}), 948(\text{s}), 882(\text{s}), 839(\text{s}), 731(\text{s}), 708(\text{s})$; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , room temperature, δ) : 8.39 (2H, s), 8.30 (4H, d), 7.98 (4H, d), 7.42–7.51 (8H, m), 4.66–4.76 (4H, q), 3.91–3.94 (1H, m), 2.97 (2H, t), 2.84 (2H, t).

A solution of iodoethanol (0.932 g, 5.421 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of 1,3-bis[(anthracene-2-ylmethyl)-amino]-propan-2-ol (1.160 g, 2.464 mmol) and K_2CO_3 (1.022 g, 7.393 mmol) in 50 ml of dry acetone and the reaction mixture was refluxed for ~ 6 h. Then the reaction mixture was stirred over night resulting in the formation of a deep brown solution. The deep brown solution was filtered to discard any insoluble precipitate. The solution was then evaporated to dryness under vacuum to isolate a brown solid product which was washed with acetone and hexane. The product was dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} . The product was confirmed by elemental analysis, FTIR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy. Yield : 1.2 g (82%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 79.56; H, 7.53; N, 4.76. Found : C, 79.61; H, 7.44; N, 4.57%; FTIR (cm^{-1}) : $\nu = 3339(\text{b}), 2924(\text{b}), 1657(\text{s}), 1623(\text{s}), 1523(\text{s}), 1445(\text{s}), 1382(\text{s}), 1340(\text{s}), 1260(\text{s}), 1158(\text{s}), 1048(\text{s}), 1018(\text{s}), 887(\text{s}), 841(\text{s}), 732(\text{s}), 601(\text{s})$; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , room temperature, δ) : 8.25 (2H, s), 8.15 (4H, d), 7.82 (4H, d), 7.44–7.48 (4H, t), 7.32–7.35 (4H, t), 4.58 (4H, s), 3.74–3.83 (1H, m), 3.37–3.45 (4H, m), 2.75–2.81 (4H, t), 2.51–2.55 (4H, t); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , room temperature, δ) : 131.11, 131.05, 129.31, 129.05, 127.32, 125.21, 125.09, 124.95, 123.65, 64.65, 64.06, 63.27, 57.53, 56.29.

Synthesis of [Cu₂L(μ-OAc)(H₂O)₂] (1) :

A solution of Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O (0.178 g, 0.90 mmol) in 10 ml methanol was added to a solution of H₃L (0.250 g, 0.45 mmol) and NaOH (0.054 g, 1.35 mmol) in 15 ml methanol with magnetic stirring during a period of 10 min. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h resulting in a green solution. Gradually, a green solid compound was separated out and the product was collected by filtration through a glass frit. The compound was recrystallized from methanol-dimethyl sulphoxide (3 : 1; v/v) solution, washed with methanol and hexane and finally dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀ as crystalline **1**. Yield : 0.30 g (90%). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₉H₄₂N₂O₇Cu₂ : C, 60.22; H, 5.44; N, 3.60; Cu, 16.34. Found : C, 59.98; H, 5.65; N, 3.71; Cu, 16.13%; FTIR (cm⁻¹) : ν = 3402(b), 1623(s), 1564(s), 1428(s), 1340(s), 1257(s), 1180(s), 1056(s), 980(s), 891(s), 736(s), 674(s), 535(s). Molar conductance, Λ_M : (DMF) = 17 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹; UV-Vis (DMSO) : λ_{max} (ε, L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) = 677 (160), 390 (15860), 370 (19900), 353 (14820), 336 (10020).

Synthesis of [Zn₂L(μ-Cl)(H₂O)₂] (2) :

A solution of ZnCl₂ (0.123 g, 0.90 mmol) in 10 ml methanol was added to a solution of H₃L (0.250 g, 0.45 mmol) and NaOH (0.054 g, 1.35 mmol) in 15 ml methanol with magnetic stirring during a period of 10 min. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h resulting in a light yellow solution. Gradually, a light yellow solid compound was separated out and the product was collected by filtration. The compound was recrystallized from methanol solution, washed with methanol and hexane and finally dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀ as crystalline **2**. Yield : 0.28 g (87%). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₇H₃₉N₂O₅ClZn₂ : C, 58.63; H, 5.19; N, 3.70; Zn, 17.25. Found : C, 58.49; H, 5.45; N, 3.89; Zn, 17.33%; FTIR (cm⁻¹) : ν = 3447(b), 1623(s), 1524(s), 1493(s), 1446(s), 1284(s), 1341(s), 1256(s), 1158(s), 1058(s), 956(s), 891(s), 735(s), 713(s), 666(s), 526(s). Molar conductance, Λ_M : (DMF) = 24 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹; UV-Vis (DMSO) : λ_{max} (ε, L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) = 389 (17340), 370 (18400), 351 (12060), 335 (6048); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, room temperature, δ) : 7.83–8.41 (10H, m, aromatic), 7.29–7.57 (8H, m, aromatic), 2.57–4.63 (17H, m, ethylenic); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, room temperature, δ) : 131.40, 131.28, 130.98, 129.41, 129.22, 127.58, 126.17, 125.58, 125.41, 67.28, 64.23, 59.63, 56.70, 51.82.

UV-Vis spectroscopy :

All experiments were performed on a Shimadzu UV 1800 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell at room temperature over a range of 200–900 nm. All experiments were done in degassed DMSO solution, in which pH was adjusted to pH ~12.5 with NaOH prior to the use for each set of titration. Typically, 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ M stock solution of each complex and 40 × 10⁻⁴ M stock solution of each substrate were prepared separately and kept at room temperature. The total concentration of complex (V_{complex} = 1.5 ml; [complex]_t = 1.25 × 10⁻⁴ M) and the total volume of the resulting solutions (V_t = 3 ml) were kept constant during the titration experiments (V_{substrate} = 0–1.5 ml) by adding an appropriate amount of DMSO. The UV-Vis absorbance and the pH meter readings of the resulting mixtures were measured immediately after mixing.

Fluorescence spectroscopy :

The fluorescence titrations were performed using a Perkin-Elmer-LS55 spectrofluorimeter equipped with FLWINLAB software with a rectangular quartz cuvette of path length 1 cm at room temperature. All experiments were done in degassed DMSO solution, in which pH was adjusted to pH ~12.5 with NaOH prior to use for each set of titration. A DMSO solution (2 ml) of each complex (6.25 × 10⁻⁴ M) was titrated by consecutive addition of the respective sugar substrates (0–1.3 × 10⁻³ M). The solution was excited at the 370 nm. Upon addition of respective sugar solution, the change in fluorescence emission of complexes **1** and **2** were observed. The corresponding emission values during titration were documented and used for the evaluation of binding constant values.

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